

Supplementary Table 3. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the electrical conductivity test considering a time-dependent model for *J. mollissima* seeds.

Source of Variation	F	p-value
	197340.00	< 0.0001 **
Lot	102,47	0.0001**
Seed Quantity	2.18	0.1995
Temperature	127,08	<0.0001 **
Water Volume	313,33	<0.0001 **
Immersion time	1197.82	<0.0001 **
Seed Quantity x Temperature	35.48	0.0001 **
Seed Quantity x Water Volume	15.06	0.0009 **
Temperature x Water Volume	0.05	0.8338

** Significant at 5% significance. Data with logarithmic transformation.